
Consumer Confidence under Inflationary Pressures: An OLS-Based Analysis of Pakistan's Economy

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Abstract:

This study investigates the impact of rising prices on consumer confidence in Pakistan using annual secondary time series data from 2000 to 2025. Employing the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) methodology, the analysis begins with descriptive statistics and unit root tests, which confirm stationarity of the variables after first-order differencing. The Ramsey RESET test indicates no significant specification errors, validating the functional form of the model. The empirical findings reveal that higher prices significantly undermine consumer confidence, highlighting the critical role of consumer perceptions in shaping economic activity. As consumer confidence influences decisions on spending and saving, the study underscores its importance for understanding aggregate demand and economic stability. The results further suggest that policies aimed at maintaining price stability, curbing market inefficiencies, and enhancing consumer trust are essential for sustaining economic growth.

Keywords: Consumer confidence; Inflation; Price stability; Economic activity; Pakistan; Ordinary Least Squares (OLS); Time series analysis

1. Introduction:

Consumer decision-making behavior has long been recognized as a central theme in market analysis, as it reflects the complex interplay of factors that shape purchasing outcomes. Within the marketplace, individuals are continuously confronted with numerous choices, where the act of pu

urchase represents one of the most critical decision-making processes. These choices are influenced by a variety of elements, including personal preferences, social interactions, recommendations from others, and the trade-offs made to secure the most advantageous option. Equally important, the quality and availability of products in the market serve as decisive factors that further guide consumer behavior.

As a criterion, consumer confidence is considered as a critical indicator of economic agents' standards, expectations and sentiments. Understanding consumer behavior is an important task for the policymakers to initiate effective monetary and fiscal policies. In the modern era, which is certainly influenced by e-commerce and social media, consumers can easily compare products and services regarding their prices. The increasing trend of globalization has contributed prominently to creating issues of economies of scale.

Furthermore, consumer behavior is a result of personal choices, thoughts, sentiments and actions that a consumer has to imply during purchasing a particular good or service. In this state, the decisions of the buyer can easily be concluded from their behaviour; here, the consumer focuses on what, why, where, when, and how to buy. After undergoing a certain decision-making process, these decisions turn into actions that we can state as consumer behavior. All the prior process is again influenced by prices, so unquestionably price is a very prominent market indicator. However, the price of a good or service narrates the amount of economic outlay required to purchase that certain good or service. So, in contrast, if the prices are high, consumers might hesitate in purchasing. Simply we can state that price is partially the "Price Effect".

Following this precisely effective method, it is obvious that fluctuation in prices may affect consumer's purchasing decision to a large extent. Many researchers have debated on price being a confusing motivator for consumers. They do not perceive the price of a good or service as its value but as a deduction in their monetary resources. It has a negative influence on buying behaviour.

Consumer confidence represents gross stability of an economy as it represents the ability of individuals to purchase things in an economy like Pakistan, where inflation and unemployment denotes continual instability, high movements in consumer confidence and market demand signify upcoming economic challenges for the economy. It is important to examine these stages for financial institutions, government authorities, policy makers and businesses as consumer confidence effects aggregate demand and ambit of economic growth to a large extent.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The purpose of the proposed study is to investigate some of the issues that may be positively or negatively related to high costs and how they affect the choices made by consumers. Accordingly, this research seeks to achieve the following goals.

- To ascertain how Pakistani consumers' confidence is affected by inflation (high prices).
- To ascertain the impact of Pakistan's unemployment rate on consumer confidence.
- To conduct a thorough analysis of Pakistani prices and consumer confidence
- To offer suggestions to policymakers regarding the potential benefits of minimum prices for Pakistani consumers and to suggest improved policies for appropriate price settlement and boosting consumer confidence in the purchase of goods and services.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Building on the outlined objectives, this study seeks to empirically examine the factors influencing consumer confidence in Pakistan. Given the persistent challenges of inflation and unemployment in the country, it is expected that these macroeconomic variables exert significant pressure on consumer sentiment and decision-making behavior. Moreover, fluctuations in prices and market inefficiencies may weaken consumer trust, while appropriate policy interventions, such as the introduction of minimum pricing mechanisms and measures to stabilize markets, may enhance consumer confidence. To investigate these relationships systematically, the following hypotheses are proposed.

Ho: Inflation (high prices) has no significant impact on consumer confidence in Pakistan.

H₁: Inflation (high prices) has a significant negative impact on consumer confidence in Pakistan.

OUTLINE OF STUDY

According to the study's structure, the introduction is presented in section 1, the theoretical and empirical literature reviews are presented in sections 2 and 3, the methodology and data source are presented in section 4, the primary data analysis is explained in section 5, the model estimation results are presented in section 6, and the conclusion, policy implications, and future direction are presented in section 7.

2. Literature Review:

The study discovers a robust body of literature outlining how high costs in an economy affect consumers' decisions to buy. Numerous more elements may impact a consumer's decision or purchase. As stated in the economics history, the law of demand characterizes a commodity's price as a premium factor that affects the quantity requested in pain. The quantity demanded for that particular commodity will decrease as the price increases. In addition to price, other considerations include consumer income, economic fashion trends, population size, the cost of alternatives, and the launch of new companies. Each of these factors influences the consumer's choice to buy a commodity. Here are some studies that examine the relationship between various factors that affect consumers' purchase decisions.

According to Kotler and Keller (2016), consumer decisions for purchases are mainly made by the consumers' perceptions of prices, which is an important source of their knowledge of the product. Likewise, Komaladevi and Indika (2017) concluded that price is still a dominant factor of influence when deciding to purchase. Consistent with this, Albari and Indah (2015), found that price-related phenomena are an important issue in the decision making of consumers as a whole. Similarly, Al-Mamun and Rehman (2014), explains that consumers act rationally when weighing up the anticipated advantages they will obtain that are relative to the payments they make for the goods and services provided. Additionally, a study by S. Afsheen and S. Khan (2012) found that prices have a greater effect on consumer purchasing than any other factor. A study by Feltovich and N Anbarci (2017) examined the impact of pricing information on purchasers' levels. They draw the conclusion that prices have an impact on the perceptions of both buyers and sellers. According to B. Lester's (2011) research on price information with capacity limitations, customers who possess greater knowledge about the pricing of items tend to purchase them at

higher prices. The study by Engelmann and Tyran (2005) comes to the conclusion that both buy boycotts and demand withholding are signs of decreased efficiency and have an influence on prices.

A study demonstrated a favourable correlation between consumer purchasing decisions and inflation (M Sata, 2013). However, a study by Murova and R Muhammed (2019) examined the US yogurt industry and found a direct correlation between consumer purchasing decisions and basket pricing of goods. The evidence presented in Eva Mueller (1996) demonstrates that the fall in consumer optimism is primarily a result of the unemployment rate. Akhtar and Shahnaz (2005), according to the study Pakistan's unemployment rate has been rising over time. The main causes of the increase in the unemployment rate in the 1990s were financial tightness, slow economic growth, and other causes.

However, according to S.C. Ludvigson's (2005) study survey, consumer confidence is a reflection of both income expectations and the growth of wealth outside of the stock market. Research evidence is produced based on a mixed relationship between surveys and preventive saving objectives. Additionally, a study by Matsusaka and Sbordone (1995) examined the connection between GDP growth and the Michigan Index of Consumer Sentiment (MICS). According to the study, MICS is the difference between real interest rates, national income, inflation, and unemployment. Michael and Evgenia (2006) also had a finding that confidence of consumers is a predictor of future macro activity and results of small stock, over the past twenty years. Earlier, Scott and Acemoglu (1994) cited the Consumer Confidence Index (CCI) as an important indicator of consumption. They outlined that consumption can be explained by inflation, real interest rates, housing wealth, as well as consumer confidence. Benhabib, J Wang et al (2015) illustrated that real earnings, productivity choices, and aggregate demand in the economy typically shape consumer confidence. Therefore, even in the absence of any externalities and full rationalization of expectations, there is still evidence that confidence shocks impact output and employment. Mamtaz & Surico's (2018) findings illustrated how shocks

arising from economic policy uncertainty negatively affect business and consumer confidence. The study results sadly suggest that uncertainty around the public debt level negatively affects consumer confidence. Overall, public debt due to uncertainty negatively affects overall levels of output.

Vanlaer et al. (2020) emphasize that uncertainty decreases consumer confidence which negatively influence consumer behavior and household saving. Still in this environment, Bergman and Worm (2020) study economic policy uncertainty and its effect on consumer confidence and household expectations. Their findings show that policy uncertainty has a strong effect on household financial outlook and consumer attitude overall. Nowzohour and Stracca (2020) study consumer confidence together with economic policy uncertainty and stock market volatility. Their findings suggest that consumer confidence tend to be linked with global economic uncertainty and financial market volatility. Here, A.A.S. Syed et al. (2022) examined the effect of economic policy unpredictability on Pakistani consumers' confidence index. The study's findings show that shocks to Pakistan's economic policy uncertainty have a negative and considerable impact on the consumer confidence index. The results indicate that price levels influence consumer decision making in a positive way. Sudeshna (2021) also understands the relationship between the policies of uncertainty and consumer confidence based on the case of Japan. Similarly, De and Almei

da (2019) examine whether uncertainty and policy level macroeconomic variables affect business confidence and consumer confidence. Their findings demonstrate that greater uncertainty in policies and lower credibility harm confidence among consumers.

In the area of global consumer spending, the International Monetary Fund (IMF,2023) points to much higher near-term inflation expectations in the post-pandemic recovery phase of most economies, which came after significant cost-push shocks in 2022 that included an unexpected rise in energy and commodity prices, as well as significant supply chain delivery dates. The IMF also points out that inflation expectations increased across the board for professional forecasters, financial market participants, households, and firms. Bernanke and Blanchard (2023) also reviewed the U.S. economy state and came to a conclusion that the sharp rise in inflation in the U.S. economy was affiliated with commodity risen series and sector specific risen prices and not wage growth. Ball et al. (2022) found the rise in the median inflation in the U.S. was due to tight labor market conditions. Also, IMF researchers (Mai Chi Dao, Dizioli, Jackson, Gourinchas, & Leigh)(2023) argued that accompanying monetary policy inflationary pressures with tight fiscal policy should complement monetary policy to assist to limit aggregate demand.

Dun & Bradstreet Pakistan, in collaboration with Gallup Pakistan, released the Consumer Confidence Index (CCI) for May 2025. The May 2025 edition of the CCI suggests improved consumer confidence among individuals concerning the economic situation as a whole and their individual financial circumstances. The other survey driven by the State Bank of Pakistan and the Institute of Business Administration Karachi, is the Consumer Confidence Survey (CCS), which does a national survey. Starting from the July 2025 survey in the CCS, it will shift its survey questions on inflation expectations from rupee-denominated to percentage change. This change was made following anticipation that this may mitigate instability in responses. Inayat

(2024) suggests that consumers reacted to the exchange rate regime shift, and offered the evidence that individuals elongated their time perspective after deliberately using a managed float exchange rate policy instead of a fixed exchange rate policy. This is a clear example of how changes in economic policies directly shape consumers' expectation formation.

In addition, CCI (Quarter 04, 2024) suggests any economic factors as concerns significantly declined throughout 2024 due to inflation dropping from the highest concerns being 16 percentage points lower for Pakistanis-its lowest worries with inflation in three and a half years. Retail activity in Pakistan has increased. However, the same report indicates that consumer confidence in taking on significant expenditures has decreased. Only 4% of Pakistanis felt comfortable to make an expenditure in the \$1000 range by Q4.

akistan from 2000 to 2025, obtained from (World Bank, and Trading Economics). The regression model by Least Squares (OLS) for the prices were represented as the

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 X^2 + \beta_3 X^3$$

Economics equation:

$$CC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PR + \beta_2 UR + \mu t$$

Where,

$Y = CC$ (Consumer Confidence), β_0 = Intercept/slope, β_1 = Coefficient of PR (Prices), β_2 Coefficient of UR (Unemployment Rate).

t = time series data. μ = Error term.

Assumption: Expected sign of β_1 would be negative.

4. Estimation Results:

4.1. Test result for normality check:

Series: Residuals	
Sample 2000 2023	
Observations 24	
Mean	-5.18e-15
Median	-0.880618
Maximum	7.465446
Minimum	-6.435954
Std.Dev.	3.434134
Skewness	0.258947
Kurtosis	2.375146
Jarque-Bera	0.658657
Probability	0.719406

The research used time series data and we performed the Normality test in EViews. The Jarque-Bera test confirmed null hypothesis was accepted since the probability value was more than 0.05, indicating residuals were normally distributed. The residuals also have positive values for the skewness coefficient indicating the residuals to be positively distributed. The kurtosis value was below three indicated that the residuals are platykurtic.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive Statistics			
	CC	PR	UR
Mean	33.10417	8.61078	2.235292
Median	34.5	7.80662	1.315
Maximum	51	20.28612	6.4
Minimum	15	2.529328	0.4
Std.Dev	9.762371	4.835594	1.956172
Skewness	-0.104991	0.835594	0.692774
Kurtosis	2.154891	3.234572	2.204128
Jarque-Bera	0.758302	2.847894	2.553156
Probability	0.684442	0.240762	0.27899
Sum	842.5	206.6587	53.647
Sum of Squares	2191.99	542.3952	88.01198

Descriptive statistics from the time series dataset were done. The Jarque-Bera test (done in EViews) for CC, PR, and UR indicates the probability values for the three variables to be above 0.05 indicating that series for CC, PR and UR originate from normally distributed populations.

Following this, the shape of the distribution (skewness) was assessed using descriptive statistics. The skewness coefficients indicate that CC, PR, and UR are positively skewed since the mean is higher than its respective medians

- In terms of kurtosis, the coefficient for CC is less than three indicating a platykurtic distribution. The kurtosis value for PR is greater than three indicating a leptokurtic distribution. UR has a kurtosis coefficient of less than three indicating that UR also exhibited a platykurtic distribution.

4.4. Regression Estimation:

Table 4.4.1: Simple Regression Model Estimation:

Dependent Variable: CC
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 05/06/23 Time: 14:43
 Sample: 2000 2023
 Included observations: 24

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	43.21337	1.650167	26.18727	0.0000
PR	-1.686459	0.156429	-10.78099	0.0000
UR	2.868760	0.388333	7.387376	0.0000
R-squared	0.876256	Mean dependent var		35.10417
Adjusted R-squared	0.864471	S.D. dependent var		9.762371
S.E. of regression	3.593946	Akaike info criterion		5.512847
Sum squared resid	271.2454	Schwarz criterion		5.660104
Log likelihood	-63.15416	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.551914
F-statistic	74.35266	Durbin-Watson stat		1.480547
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

As shown in Table 4.3.1, the null hypothesis is rejected as the probability value is less than 0.05, indicating the model is statistically significant. The R-squared value of 0.87 indicates that the independent variables in the model account for 87% of the variation in consumer confidence.

Graph 4.4.1 Actual Residual Fitted Line Graph:

4.5. Correlation Matrix:

	CC	PR	UR
CC	1	-0.744	0.4374

PR	-0.744	1	0.1637
UR	0.4374	0.1637	1

The table indicates a positive association between the unemployment rate and inflation and a negative correlation between consumer confidence and inflation.

4.6. Stationary Check by using ADF Unit Root test:

ADF				
At Level		1st Difference		Decision
		C&T	C&T	
CC	t-statistics	-3.157	-3.948	1(1)
	P-Value	0.125	0.02	
PR	t-statistics	-2.101	-5.458	1(1)
	P-Value	0.516	0	
UR	t-statistics	-2.005	-6.99	1(1)
	P-Value	0.56	0.0001	

In this table, you can also see the results of the Unit Root Test, which was conducted using EViews software. The p-values at level are larger than 0.05, which indicate the values are non-stationary. The p-values fall below 0.05 at first difference, showing that the variables become stationary and are integrated at order I(1).

4.7. Ramsey RESET:

Table 4.7.1: Ramsey RESET of Model:

Ramsey RESET Test			
	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	1.686587	20	0.1072
F-statistic	2.844574	(1,20)	0.1072
Likelihood ratio	3.191553	1	0.0741

: there is no specification

Forecast:CCF	
Actual:CC	
Forecast sample:2000 2023	
Included observations:24	
Root Mean Squared Error	3.361828
Mean Absolute Error	2.902351
Mean Abs. Percent Error	0.046301
Theil Inequality Coef.	0.000000
Bias Proportion	0.033012
Variance Proportion	0.966988
Covariance Proportion	
Theil U2 Coefficient	0.506637
Symmetric MAPE	9.188812

This regression model is an in-sample forecast because it uses the real values of the independent variables. The Theil's inequality coefficient in Table 4.7.1 is very close to zero, which demonstrates the forecasting performance of the model.

5. Model Estimation Result:

Estimation Equation:

$$CC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PR + \beta_2 UR + \mu_t$$

Substituted Coefficients:

$$CC = 43.2133739978 - 1.68645860406 * PR + 2.8687603431 * UR$$

The results suggest that when prices increase by 1 unit, consumer confidence decreased by 1.68 units. The testing of the hypothesis is at the .05 probability level. Since the p-values are less than .05, the model is significant, which means that inflation (increasing prices) has a significant negative impact on consumer confidence. As expected, the negative parameter of β indicates that the independent variable reduced the dependent variable that is customer confidence.

6. Conclusion and Policy Implication:

The model's findings reveal an inverse relationship between consumer confidence and inflationary pressures, indicating that elevated price levels exert a significant negative influence on consumer sentiment. This outcome underscores the theoretical proposition that inflation erodes real purchasing power, thereby constraining consumer welfare and diminishing overall confidence in economic stability.

From a theoretical perspective, these results suggest that institutional and structural mechanisms play a crucial role in shaping consumer perceptions. Price distortions arising from corruption, black-market activities, or artificial stockpiling of essential goods amplify the adverse effects of inflation on consumer confidence. Hence, ensuring price stability through mechanisms aligned with purchasing power parity and reducing market inefficiencies may foster greater consumer trust, enhance satisfaction, and support more rational decision-making within the economy.

These findings also highlight the need for targeted policy interventions. Government efforts to stabilize prices—such as aligning them with purchasing power parity, addressing corruption and black-market practices, and discouraging artificial stockpiling of essential goods—would help restore consumer confidence. By ensuring fair market practices and maintaining price stability, policymakers can strengthen consumer trust, promote more informed decision-making, and foster greater resilience in the economy.

7. Limitation and Direction for further research:

This study is subject to certain limitations that should be acknowledged. Due to the unavailability of comprehensive data, the analysis was confined to selected time periods between 2000 and 2025, utilizing annual secondary time series data. Furthermore, although a variety of econometric techniques could have been employed to enhance the robustness of the findings, the study relied solely on the ordinary least squares (OLS) method for model estimation.

In terms of research scope, the study examined the impact of price increases within a relatively limited temporal framework. Future research could address this gap by extending the analysis over a longer horizon, as larger sample sizes and longer time series generally improve the accuracy of estimates while reducing potential biases and margins of error. Additionally, in order to gain a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between rising costs and consumer confidence, subsequent studies are encouraged to employ higher-frequency datasets, such as quarterly or monthly observations, which may capture short-term dynamics more effectively.

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